

**An Assessment of Sustainability Reporting in some Selected Oil and Gas Companies in
Nigeria**

Dissertation

**submitted for the award of MSc International Business Management
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by

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Declaration

I declare that this research project has not already been accepted in substance for any degree and is not concurrently submitted in candidature for any degree. It is the result of my own independent research except where otherwise stated.

Signed ...**Kilani Ibrahim.**

Dated**May 2024.**

Abstract

This dissertation assessed the sustainability reporting practices of selected Nigerian oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. It evaluated the extent, content, and emphasis on areas of sustainability disclosures across the environmental, economic, and social dimensions. The study employed a quantitative research design, analysing secondary data from annual reports and standalone sustainability reports using the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) framework.

Findings revealed a gradual improvement in overall sustainability disclosure levels from 2019 to 2022, with significant variations across companies. Environmental reporting witnessed notable progress, while economic and social disclosures remained relatively consistent. However, companies prioritized social responsibility and community engagement disclosures, potentially utilizing them as "Authorizing veneers" to manage legitimacy amidst environmental impacts. The quality and comprehensiveness of reporting still lagged global best practices.

The study concluded that while sustainability reporting is improving in the Nigerian oil and gas sector, companies need to provide more balanced and transparent disclosures that address all ESG aspects credibly. Recommendations included implementing stringent disclosure policies, capacity building, stakeholder engagement, and further research to enhance sustainability reporting practices, transparency, and accountability in the industry.

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List of Abbreviations

Corporate Affairs Commission	(CAC)
Environmental, Social, and Governance.....	(ESG)
Global Reporting Initiative.....	(GRI)
Nigerian Stock Exchange.....	(NSE)

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CHAPTER ONE

Introduction

1.1 Background

The global discourse on corporate sustainability reporting has intensified in recent years as businesses recognize the significance of integrating environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors into their reporting (Smith, 2021) and this trend is reinforced by the increasing adoption of reporting standards like the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI). This shift reflects a growing awareness of the need for sustainable business practices that balance profitability with social and environmental responsibility (Nwobu et al., 2021). In the oil and gas industry in Nigeria, sustainability reporting has become a crucial tool for fostering transparency, accountability, and ethical business practices (Ezejiolor et al., 2022). Sustainability reporting (SR) involves measuring, disclosing, and being accountable to internal and external stakeholders to achieve sustainable development goals (GRI, 2011) such as affordable and clean energy, clean water and sanitation, decent work and economic growth, and climate action. Companies that report on sustainability provide information about their environmental, social, and governance (ESG) policies, practices, impacts, and performance (Herzig and Schaltegger, 2006), seeing it as essential to demonstrate accountability, ensure regulatory compliance, manage risks, seize opportunities, and build trust with stakeholders in an evolving business landscape. A growing proportion of organizations globally issue yearly sustainability reports in addition to financial accounts (KPMG, 2020) reasons been that issuing sustainability reports alongside financial accounts aligns with evolving stakeholder expectations, helps manage risks, enhances competitiveness, and can facilitate access to capital.

The importance of sustainability reporting in the oil and gas sector lies in its capacity to address the multifaceted challenges posed by the industry, such as environmental and social impacts relating to climate change, pollution, health and safety, labour practices, and community relations (Stella Emeka-Okoli et al., 2024). For example, Chevron's 2022 Corporate Sustainability Report shows the company's efforts to address key sustainability issues, including plans to end routine flaring by 2030.

Nigeria, an emerging economy with a primary focus on petroleum and other solid mineral endowments, is confronted with significant environmental degradation due to the oil and gas industry's exploration and exploitation activities (Onoja, A. et al., 2022). This is evidence in multiple oil spillages in Nigeria's Niger Delta, including the Batan pipeline spill in 2002 (Amnesty International, 2008) and the recent OML29 Well 1 spill in 2021 (OMEF, 2021).

Hence, there is a need for oil and gas companies in Nigeria to report on their sustainability reporting for accountability to stakeholders.

This project seeks to shed light on the current level of sustainability reporting in selected Nigerian oil and gas listed firms and how these companies report their sustainability engagement and involvement.

1.2 Problem Statement

Oil and gas companies often aim to maximize firm value while remaining profitable, but their activities can have both positive and negative impacts on the environment (Clarkson et al., 2011; Horvathova, 2010). Governments and non-governmental organizations are calling for more sustainability reporting, disclosure, and awareness. However, Nigerian oil and gas corporations fail to fully embrace and comply with globally recognized frameworks like the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), raising concerns about the comprehensiveness and credibility of their sustainability information (Smith & Jones, 2022).

Despite the significant environmental and social impacts of the oil and gas industry in Nigeria, there is limited transparency and accountability around sustainability practices by domestic companies. The cost of adopting sustainability practices is often cited as a barrier (Nwaiwu et al., 2018). Without clear public disclosure of key ESG metrics, stakeholders have difficulty assessing the sustainability performance and risks associated with major Nigerian energy companies.

Inadequate corporate sustainability reporting by local players contributes to existing accountability gaps. Therefore, research is needed to analyse the status of sustainability reporting by Nigeria's listed oil and gas companies, compare their practices to global standards, and identify opportunities to strengthen transparency and responsible business conduct.

1.3 Research Objectives

The objectives of this research are:

To assess the sustainability reporting engagement of the selected Nigerian oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange

To analyse the content and scope of published sustainability reports.

To examine emphasis placed by selected Nigerian oil and gas companies on the environmental, economic, and social dimensions of sustainability in their public reporting, and identify any neglected areas.

1.4 Research Questions

The main research question.

How do oil and gas companies in Nigeria report their sustainability engagement and involvement?

Sub-questions.

What dimension among the three—environment, economics, and social—received more emphasis, and which ones were neglected?

What sustainability indicators do Nigerian oil and gas companies include and track in their public reporting? Do they align with global industry best practices?

1.5 Significance of the Study

The research on sustainability reporting of oil and gas companies in Nigeria is important as it addresses the growing concern for the environmental and social impact of the oil and gas industry, particularly in a country like Nigeria with a significant presence of such companies (Onwuadi, et al. 2022).

However, most research on sustainability reporting in Africa has focused on South Africa so far with limited scholarly focus on Nigeria specifically. Existing studies often focus on developed economies, creating a gap in understanding the unique dynamics of a developing nation like Nigeria (Onoja, et al 2021). This study will contribute to filling this gap.

Findings may reveal potential factors that can influence Nigerian oil and gas companies towards better disclosure. Furthermore, the project's outcomes may contribute to the existing body of knowledge on sustainability reporting in the context of oil and gas companies, potentially informing future academic research and literature.

This research consists of six chapters. The first chapter introduces the study, while the second delves into the research background and introduces essential subject components. The third chapter analyses relevant literature and theoretical framework, while the fourth part discusses the methodology employed. Chapter five offers the research findings, while Chapter six concludes the study's findings while offering recommendations.

CHAPTER TWO

Research Context

The contextual chapter of this study will explore the historical, social, and cultural factors that have influenced the development of sustainability reporting in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. By examining historical trends, societal expectations, and cultural dynamics, the study seeks to assess the current state of sustainability reporting in selected Nigerian oil and gas companies.

2.1 Historical Context

According to Osagioduwa et al. (2023), Nigeria's journey towards sustainability has been complex, marked by the interplay of socio-economic factors, environmental challenges, and the quest for sustainable development. As the most populous country in Africa, Nigeria is blessed with abundant natural resources, including oil, gas, and a diverse ecosystem (World Bank, 2021). However, the exploitation of these resources, combined with rising urbanization and population growth, has created significant challenges to the country's sustainability. One critical part of Nigeria's sustainability journey is the realization of the importance of balancing economic development and environmental protection. The country's experience with oil extraction and production serves as a compelling case study in this regard. Nigeria's oil business, established in the 1950s, has generated substantial wealth for the nation, but it has also led to environmental degradation, pollution, and socioeconomic disparities (Ovadia, 2019).

Inclusion of sustainability reporting in Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC) regulations (2003). The Corporate Affairs Commission included sustainability reporting as part of its regulations for the annual reports of Nigerian companies. This marked an early recognition of the importance of reporting on social and environmental aspects (CAC, 2003). Establishment of the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) in Nigeria (2013): The GRI established its first African Regional Hub in Nigeria, which aimed to support organizations in adopting sustainability reporting practices aligned with the GRI framework. This initiative enhanced awareness and capacity-building for sustainability reporting in the country.

Sustainability reporting in the Nigerian oil and gas industry has gained increasing importance in recent years as the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) has implemented a phased project to integrate sustainability reporting for its listed companies (Onoja et al., 2021). This process began in 2015 and included hosting a sustainability conference, developing Sustainability Disclosure Guidelines, and holding a seminar to educate stakeholders on the reporting format and value proposition (NSE Sustainability Disclosure Guidelines 2018). Studies have shown that the oil and gas sector is one of the industries spearheading the charge for sustainable

development due to the highly visible negative impacts of its operations, such as oil spills (Okutu et al., 2024). In Nigeria, the adoption of sustainability reporting by oil and gas companies has also been driven by factors such as pressure from civil society organizations like the Niger Delta Human and Environmental Rescue Organization (NDHERO), the Institute for Human Rights and Humanitarian Law (IHRHL), and indigenous communities for the need to address environmental and social challenges. However, the level of sustainability reporting among Nigerian oil and gas companies has been mixed, with some companies making more progress than others (Onoh et al., 2023).

2.2 Cultural Context

Cultural factors like power distance, individualism and collectivism, uncertainty avoidance may play a significant role in shaping sustainability reporting practices in Nigeria (Benvenuto et al., 2023). One of the key cultural norms that may influence sustainability reporting is the emphasis on community and collective well-being (Idemudia, 2011). Nigerian society places a strong value on social responsibility and the need for businesses to contribute positively to their local communities. This cultural norm could potentially drive companies to prioritize and disclose their sustainability efforts, particularly in areas such as community development and social investment, rather than solely on financial performance (Emeni et al., 2014).

Haniffa and Cooke (2005) assert that cultures exert an effect on the behaviours of boards of directors and their endorsement of transparency procedures. The authors noted that if family members on the board feel threatened by governmental forces, then they promote secrecy and avoid disclosure. Additionally, the power distance and hierarchical structure prevalent in Nigerian culture may affect the transparency and stakeholder engagement in the sustainability report. Organizations may be less inclined to disclose sensitive information or involve diverse stakeholders in the reporting process, as this could be perceived as challenging the established power structures. Individuals in lower hierarchical positions possess limited authority and a diminished inclination towards sustainability matters. Consequently, only those occupying the uppermost echelons have the authority to determine whether to provide information to stakeholders. (Grey et al., 2003). The level of difficulty in implementing sustainability increases as the distance between levels increases. However, the empirical study conducted by García-Sánchez et al. (2013) on a sample of 1590 enterprises showed that this aspect does not appear to be the main determinant in the adoption of sustainability reporting. Understanding these cultural factors is crucial for developing effective sustainability reporting frameworks and practices that resonate with Nigerian organizations and stakeholders.

2.3 Social Context

The social context refers to the societal and community aspects that companies must consider and address in their sustainability reporting, such as stakeholder engagement, social investments, and local content and capacity building.

Stakeholders, such as local communities, environmental groups, and investors, have demanded greater transparency and accountability from oil and gas companies regarding their social and environmental performance, as there is a growing public awareness of the significant negative impacts of the industry, which include oil spills, gas flaring, and the displacement of indigenous communities (Okeke, 2021), as can be seen in the Batan pipeline spill in 2002 and the displacement of the Ogoni people in the Niger Delta of Nigeria as a result of these environmental disasters.

Sustainability reporting should, therefore, be used as an important tool for oil and gas companies to manage their social license to operate and showcase their commitment to sustainable development through the disclosure of their engagements with local communities, their support for community development initiatives, and how they mitigate any negative social impacts arising from their operations in their annual sustainability reporting (Oncioiu et al., 2020).

The social context in Nigeria demands that oil and gas companies contribute to local content development by hiring local personnel, sourcing from local suppliers, and building the capacity of local communities through skills transfer and training programs (Nigeria Oil and Gas Industry Content Development Act 2010, NOGICDA). According to the Act, an operator must provide the Content Development and Monitoring Board with a plan outlining the replacement of non-Nigerians in all positions, as well as a comprehensive strategy for Nigerian individuals to learn from and work alongside expatriates. This learning period should not exceed four years, after which the position should be filled by a qualified Nigerian. If all these were reflected in the sustainability reporting of these companies, it could address stakeholder concerns, improve their reputation, and potentially increase their financial performance (Aljanadi et al., 2023).

By addressing these social context elements in their sustainability reporting, oil and gas companies in Nigeria demonstrate their commitment to sustainable development and their recognition of the interdependence between their business operations and the well-being of local communities and society at large.

CHAPTER THREE

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

The second chapter of "An Assessment of Sustainability Reporting in Some Selected Oil and Gas Listed Companies in Nigeria" includes a review of the literature and a theoretical framework. The literature review looks at existing research on sustainable reporting. It examines significant research on the state of sustainability disclosure procedures, including reporting quality, influential factors, and impact. The theoretical framework of legitimacy theory and reputation theory was discussed in relation to corporate sustainability reporting.

3.1 Important of Oil and Gas Sector.

The fact that Nigeria's oil and gas industry is the largest contributor to the country's external reserves demonstrates the sector's economic importance. The overarching importance of the Nigerian oil and gas sector to the overall well-being of the Nigerian economy may explain the Federal Government of Nigeria's ("FGN") continuous efforts to improve the investment and operational climate in the sector (Emeka-Okoli et al., 2024).

The oil and gas sector has significantly benefited the country's economy, accounting for the bulk of government revenue and 90% of foreign exchange reserves. The sector led in terms of import and export volume and value, accounting for almost 88 percent of all exported goods and approximately 30 percent of total imports (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). This has pushed agriculture, the traditional mainstay of the economy from the early 1950s and 1960s, to the background. However, one cannot dispute that such operations have had major and significant environmental consequences for oil-producing states (Oguntoye, 2021).

Despite these challenges, the Nigerian government is committed to investing in the oil and gas industry, with plans to enhance reserves and production through field optimization and the development of marginal fields and deep-water offshore resources (US Department of Commerce, 2023). The government has also attempted to diversify the economy by investing in natural gas and energy-related sectors, as outlined in the Gas Master Plan.

Overall, the oil and gas sector remain a critical component of the Nigerian economy, but the country must address the sector's governance and environmental challenges to ensure that its oil wealth translates into sustainable economic and social development (Brookings Institution, 2021).

3.2 Review of Previous Literatures on Sustainability Reporting

Sustainability disclosures are still evolving; even when companies are in nations that mandate required reporting, adherence is mostly determined by their individual decision to report, unless there are sanctions for not reporting (Ong et al. 2016).

Nwobu, et al (2021) evaluates the extent of sustainability disclosures in the annual reports of eight oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange from 2010 to 2019. The study uses content analysis and the Global Reporting Initiative's scoring index to assess the level of economic, environmental, and social sustainability disclosures. The findings reveal a very low level of climate change and environmental pollution disclosure, with only 13.8% of companies disclosing their impact. Contrastingly, all companies reported their community investments, which the authors suggest may be a "legitimizing smokescreen" for ecological pollution. The study recommends more stringent sustainability disclosure policies to promote improved environmental compliance by oil and gas companies. Similarly, Raucci and Tarquinio (2015) and Ong et al. (2016) reported that companies disclosed more sustainability information related to economic aspects than environmental aspects. To address these concerns, the authors' recommendation for more stringent sustainability disclosure policies is well-founded. However, such policies should be accompanied by robust enforcement mechanisms, capacity-building initiatives, and engagement with industry stakeholders to promote genuine environmental accountability and sustainable practices in the Nigerian oil and gas sector.

Igwe et al. (2023) systematically review 179 high-quality journal articles from the Scopus database, focusing on sustainability reporting research in Africa. The findings reveal that the extent and quality of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and sustainability reporting in Africa are still inadequate. While existing studies primarily concentrate on the determinants of sustainability reporting. This review seeks to contextualize Igwe et al.'s findings within the scope of the assessment of sustainability reporting in Nigeria. "This finding may resonate with the broader challenges faced by Nigerian oil and gas companies in effectively communicating their sustainability efforts to stakeholders. Building upon Igwe et al.'s insights, this project endeavours to explore not only the factors driving sustainability reporting practices but also the tangible impacts and the mechanisms for ensuring the credibility and reliability of reported information. By doing so, the project can provide a more comprehensive understanding of sustainability reporting practices at Nigerian oil and gas companies.

Tijjani et al, (2020) offer a comprehensive evaluation of the extent of sustainability disclosure by listed Nigerian oil and gas companies. Utilizing the widely adopted Global Reporting

Initiative (GRI) framework, the authors analysed the sustainability reports of these companies over a five-year period from 2012 to 2016. It provides valuable insights into the extent of sustainability reporting in the Nigerian oil and gas sector. This study aligns well with the research objective of assessing sustainability reporting practices in selected Nigerian oil and gas companies. By utilizing a widely recognized framework (GRI) and focusing on a significant industry with substantial environmental and social impacts, the study offers a relevant foundation for this research project. Additionally, its examination of the factors influencing disclosure levels and the call for further research on the dimensions and determinants of sustainability reporting provide valuable directions for the research project.

In the context of assessing the factors influencing sustainability reporting practices in Nigerian oil and gas companies, the study by Hidayah et al. (2019) provides valuable insights, despite its focus on Indonesian companies. The authors investigate the determinants of sustainability reporting disclosure among companies registered with the Indonesia Sustainability Reporting Award (ISRA) over the period from 2012 to 2017. The findings reveal that a company's current ratio, which reflects its liquidity position, and the frequency of audit committee meetings have a significant positive influence on the disclosure of sustainability reports. Interestingly, the study also suggests that larger firms, contrary to expectations, tend to disclose less sustainability-related information. While these findings are based on Indonesian companies, they highlight potential factors that could be relevant to this research project on the assessment of sustainability reporting practices in selected Nigerian oil and gas companies. For instance, the liquidity position and the level of oversight by the audit committee may play a role in influencing the extent of sustainability disclosures made by these companies. Additionally, the study's finding regarding firm size warrants further investigation in the Nigerian context, as it contradicts the common assumption that larger firms tend to disclose more sustainability information.

Kabir Ibrahim et al. (2021) offers valuable insights. Their research investigates the impact of sustainability reporting on the financial performance of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Utilizing data from annual reports and standalone sustainability reports of seven publicly traded companies spanning the period from 2009 to 2019, the regression analysis revealed that environmental sustainability reporting had a positive and statistically significant effect on ROA, indicating that companies with higher levels of environmental disclosure tended to exhibit better financial performance. These findings suggest that sustainability reporting, particularly in the environmental domain, plays a crucial role in influencing the financial performance of listed Nigerian oil and gas

companies. The study underscores the importance of these companies prioritizing the disclosure of their sustainability initiatives, with a specific emphasis on environmental sustainability reporting, as it appears to be a key driver of improved financial performance.

The study by Onyebuenyi, F. E. (2023), provides an understanding of the value and relevance of environmental sustainability information disclosure, particularly carbon emission disclosure, among listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. This study aligns directly with this research topic, 'An Assessment of Sustainability Reporting in Some Selected Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria,' as it empirically investigates the state of carbon emission reporting and its implications in the Nigerian oil and gas sector. The study found that only 2% of sampled Nigerian oil and gas firms disclosed carbon emission information between 2006 and 2020, indicating poor carbon emission reporting practices. This study directly addresses a crucial aspect of sustainability reporting: environmental sustainability information disclosure, with a specific focus on carbon emission reporting. As this research project assesses sustainability reporting practices in selected Nigerian oil and gas companies, the findings from Onyebuenyi, F. E. (2023) highlight the need to evaluate the extent and quality of carbon emission disclosure, as well as the potential implications of such disclosure on investor perceptions and firm valuation.

Overall, the main themes and issues across these studies revolve around the extent, quality, and impact of sustainability reporting in the Nigerian and some other countries oil and gas sectors. The studies highlight increasing sustainability reporting but with gaps, especially in disclosing environmental and climate change impacts by oil and gas firms. They also raise critical issues regarding the effectiveness, transparency, and alignment of reporting practices with stakeholder needs and environmental concerns.

3.3 Theoretical Underpinning

This theoretical chapter discusses how legitimacy theory and reputation theory can explain the motivations and practices of sustainability reporting by Nigerian oil and gas companies.

3.3.1 Legitimacy Theory and Sustainability Reporting

The theoretical framework of legitimacy theory provides a useful lens to analyse and understand the motivations and practices of sustainability reporting in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. According to this theory, organizations seek to ensure that their activities and outputs are perceived as legitimate and congruent with the norms, values, and expectations of the broader society in which they operate (Ogiri et al. 2012). Meutia et al. (2021) explain that legitimacy theory suggests companies should disclose information about their environmental,

social, and governance (ESG) performance to demonstrate that their operations are aligned with societal expectations and norms. By reporting on their sustainability efforts, these companies can manage their relationships with key stakeholders like local communities, environmental groups, and regulators, as well as mitigate reputational risks and legitimacy threats arising from the environmental and social impacts of their operations.

The background on how sustainability reporting has become crucial for fostering transparency, accountability, and demonstrating responsible business practices in the Nigerian oil and gas sector, aligns with the core premise of legitimacy theory, which suggests that companies use sustainability reporting as a tool to legitimize their operations and align with societal expectations of ethical and sustainable conduct. While the problem statement notes the lack of comprehensive sustainability reporting by Nigerian oil and gas companies, raising concerns about accountability, from a legitimacy theory perspective, inadequate disclosure can be seen as a threat to these companies' legitimacy as stakeholders lack information to assess their true environmental and social impacts.

Ogunode, O. A. (2022), examines legitimacy theory in the literature from two perspectives: (i) institutional-level perspectives and (ii) organizational-level perspectives. While the institutional-level perspective is interested in the manner and extent to which the organization's organizational structures have received acceptance and recognition to naturally achieve organizational-set goals, because societal acceptance is critical, acceptance of any organization's products and services gives such an organization a competitive advantage over its competitors. The second part, which addresses the organizational-level perspective, is concerned with how firms, through their actions and operational activities, have protected and legitimized societal culture for it to be accepted by society.

The Research Context Chapter two, which discusses the historical context of the evolution of sustainability reporting regulations and initiatives in Nigeria, can be viewed as responses to maintain legitimacy amidst growing sustainability concerns. The cultural context highlights societal values like community well-being that oil and gas companies need to address through sustainability reporting to maintain cultural legitimacy. The social context outlines stakeholder demands for transparency on social investments and local content, which exert legitimacy pressures on companies to disclose their societal contributions.

Empirical studies applying the legitimacy theory have found that oil and gas companies in Nigeria tend to focus more on disclosing information about their social and community engagement activities than their environmental performance (Ogiri et al., 2012; Nwobu, O. et al., 2021). This suggests that these companies are primarily using sustainability reporting as a

tool to manage their legitimacy and social acceptance rather than to comprehensively address their environmental impacts.

The literatures review in Chapter three, notes studies suggesting that companies may use sustainability disclosures strategically as "legitimizing smokescreens" to project a positive image despite negative impacts. Examining such motivations through a legitimacy theory lens can provide deeper insights.

By employing legitimacy theory, the research can analyse whether and how the sustainability reporting practices of Nigerian oil and gas companies are aimed at gaining, maintaining, or repairing public confidence and societal approval for their operations, given the significant environmental and social impacts of the industry.

Overall, legitimacy theory offers an explanatory framework to interpret the findings on the extent, content, and emphasis areas of sustainability reporting by Nigerian oil and gas companies in relation to their legitimacy-seeking behaviours and motivations.

3.3.2 Reputation Theory and Sustainability Reporting

This theory suggests that companies strive to maintain a positive reputation to gain legitimacy and competitive advantage (Dušek et al., 2022). Reputation is seen as a basis for sustainability disclosure, as it allows companies to signal externally that they can sustain sound financial and market performance while also addressing social and environmental issues (Uwaoma, I., & Ordu, P. A. (2016); Dušek et al., 2022). In the context of the Nigerian oil and gas industry, where environmental and social concerns are prevalent, sustainability reporting can be a means for companies to demonstrate their commitment to responsible practices and enhance their reputation among stakeholders (Osamuade & Akadiri, 2022).

Compared to the concept of legitimacy, which focuses on conforming to the general social system, reputation theory emphasizes the social comparison between companies and the differentiation of their relative standing and provides an additional rationale for oil and gas companies in Nigeria to engage in sustainability reporting—to distinguish themselves from competitors and maintain a positive reputation (Laka et al., 2021).

In summary, reputation theory suggests that oil and gas companies in Nigeria with stronger reputations, built on factors like stakeholder commitment and financial performance, will be more likely to provide extensive sustainability reporting to preserve and enhance their standing relative to industry peers.

CHAPTER FOUR

Research Methodology

This study adopts a quantitative research design, leveraging secondary data sourced from the annual reports and sustainability stand-alone reports of selected oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). This choice is rooted in a research philosophy that values objective measurement and statistical analysis. Quantitative research offers a structured approach to gathering and analysing data, allowing for the systematic examination of phenomena and the establishment of clear patterns and relationships.

The choice of a quantitative research approach is justified by the nature of the research objective, which is to assess the level of sustainability disclosures in the annual reports of selected oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Quantitative methods are well-suited for measuring and quantifying observable phenomena, such as the presence or absence of specific sustainability indicators in corporate reports. The use of quantitative research in this project will enable empirical evidence to inform evidence-based decision-making, and the findings may provide insights for stakeholders like policymakers, investors, and corporate leaders to make informed decisions regarding sustainability practices and disclosure requirements in Nigeria's oil and gas sector. However, it's crucial to acknowledge the inherent subjectivity involved in quantitative studies relying on annual reports.

Previous research, as cited (Ramdhony et al., 2021; Sorouret al., 2020), indicates that sustainability reporting measures can be subjective and prone to measurement errors, potentially impacting the reliability of findings (Baba & Baba, 2021). Nevertheless, utilizing secondary data from annual reports is deemed appropriate for its accessibility and reliability. Annual reports, being publicly available documents providing audited financial and non-financial information, serve as a dependable and easily accessible data source.

The study's population comprises the oil and gas companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group as of January 2024 (see Appendix 2). However, due to practical constraints in accessing the entire population and to ensure specific criteria are met, a sample of seven companies was selected (see Appendix 3). The selection criteria, including market capitalization, trading activity, and consistent publication of annual reports, were implemented to ensure the sample's representativeness and alignment with the law of statistical regularity, which posits that a well-chosen sample should reflect the characteristics of its source population (Green, 2003).

The rationale behind selecting these specific companies lies in their significance within the Nigerian oil and gas sector. Focusing on the most capitalized firms with actively traded shares

and consistently published annual reports enables the study to capture the sustainability reporting practices of key industry players.

The study employs the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) 2012 indicator checklist, with adaptations from the work of Nwobu et al. (2021). The GRI framework is widely recognized in sustainability reporting, offering a comprehensive set of indicators for assessing sustainability performance. By utilizing this standardized checklist, the research ensures consistency and comparability with prior studies while allowing for adjustments to suit the Nigerian oil and gas industry's context.

The choice of a quantitative research approach is justified by the nature of the research objective, which is to assess the level of sustainability disclosures in the annual reports of selected oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Quantitative methods are well-suited for measuring and quantifying observable phenomena, such as the presence or absence of specific sustainability indicators in corporate reports.

Data analysis entails a descriptive analysis of sustainability disclosures in the annual reports. This approach facilitates quantifying and summarizing the extent of sustainability reporting among the sampled companies, aligning with the research's objective. Descriptive statistics are commonly used in quantitative studies to summarize and quantify the extent or level of a particular phenomenon, in this case, the level of sustainability reporting among the sampled companies. The data were analysed using Minitab Statistical Software (21.2.0.0). The analysis utilizes a 22-indicator checklist derived from the Global Reporting Initiative (2012), with each indicator scored as "1" if present in the reports and "0" if not. The total sustainability score is then derived from these indicators. (Refer to Appendix 1 for the indicator checklist.).

Chapter Five

Presentation and Findings

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the data and findings from a comprehensive content analysis examining the sustainability reporting practices among the seven largest indigenous Nigerian oil and gas companies. The companies analysed comprise Oando Plc (₦120.0 billion market capitalization), Total Energy (₦109.2 billion), Conoil Plc (₦69.4 billion), MRS (₦46.3 billion), Eternal Plc (₦19.8 billion), Seplat Energy (£982.38 million), and Rak Unity Petroleum (₦17.0 million) (Simply Wall St., n.d.). Collectively, these companies represent the preeminent domestic players operating within Nigeria's economically crucial oil and gas industry.

The data were derived through a systematic content analysis of each company's annual report and standalone sustainability report for the most recent fiscal years available, spanning the period from 2019 to 2022. An evaluative checklist consisting of 22 sustainability indicators grounded in the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) framework (2012) served as the coding criteria. For each company, the presence or absence of these GRI indicators within their corporate reporting was scored dichotomously, with a "1" denoting inclusion and a "0" signifying omission. The cumulative frequency of these scored indicators constitutes the quantitative data underpinning the statistical analysis (Refer to Appendix 2, 3 and 4).

The data were analysed using Minitab Statistical Software (version 21.2.0.0) to ascertain the frequency distributions (mean, minimum, maximum, range, and standard deviation) to identify patterns in the sustainability disclosures across the sample of companies. This empirical approach aims to provide insights into the current state and comprehensiveness of sustainability reporting practices within Nigeria's vital oil and gas sector.

5.2. Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Statistics of Sustainability Disclosure Scores from the Annual Report Across Sample Companies (2019-2022)

Variable: Sustainability Disclosure						
Year	Observations	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Range
2019	7	12.14	3.34	5	14	9
2020	7	11.86	4.14	4	16	12
2021	7	13	3	9	17	8
2022	7	12.71	5.82	0	17	17

Source: Compilations from Minitab Statistical Software (21.2.0.0)

In Table 1, The average sustainability disclosure score for the seven oil and gas companies gradually increased from 12.14 in 2019 to 13.00 in 2021, but slightly decreased to 12.71 in 2022. This trend shows a gradual improvement in the companies' reporting efforts, although there was a small dip in 2022. The standard deviation, which measures the variation in scores, ranged from 3.00 to 5.82 over the 4-year period. A higher standard deviation means more inconsistency in the level of disclosures among the companies. The company with the least comprehensive sustainability report, with a score of 5.00 in 2019, increased to 9.00 in 2021, indicating that even the companies with the poorest reporting improved over time. The highest sustainability disclosure scores reached 17.00 in both 2021 and 2022, reflecting the efforts of the leading companies to enhance their reporting. The range of scores (the difference between the highest and lowest scores) increased significantly from 9.00 in 2019 to 17.00 in 2022. This shows a growing gap between the best and worst performers in terms of the detail and comprehensiveness of their sustainability reporting.

Table 2: Statistics of Economic Disclosure Indicators Scores from the Annual Report Across Sample Companies (2019-2022)

Variable: Economic Disclosure						
Year	Observations	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Range
2019	7	3.143	1.069	1	4	3
2020	7	3.143	1.069	1	4	3
2021	7	3.571	1.134	2	5	3
2022	7	3.143	1.464	0	4	4

Source: Compilations from Minitab Statistical Software (21.2.0.0)

In Table 2, the mean economic disclosure scores for the 28 total observations showed little variation, hovering around 3.14 and peaking at 3.57 in 2021. This suggests a relatively stable level of economic reporting by the oil and gas companies over the 4-year period. The minimum economic disclosure scores showed some fluctuations, dropping to 0.00 in 2022. This raises concerns about at least one company not disclosing any economic metrics in that year because of the process of the voluntary winding up of the company. The maximum economic disclosure scores remained capped at 4.00 and 5.00 over the period, suggesting a ceiling in the level of detail and comprehensiveness of economic disclosures provided by the best-performing companies.

The companies in the observation disclosed their investments in the community. This may be because these companies recognize how their waste, spills, and emissions harm the host community and that investing in the community serves as a means of legitimizing their environmental pollution (Berrone et al., 2009). The climate change disclosure was appreciated, as 71.4% of companies reported on the issue. Very few companies (7.1%) reported financial assistance received from the government, and 53.5% of the companies reported spending on local suppliers at significant operations locations. Overall, the state of reporting on economic indicators in Table 2 was relatively above average.

Table 3: Statistics of Environmental Disclosure Indicators Scores from the Annual Report Across Sample Companies (2019-2022)

Variable: Environmental Disclosure						
Year	Observations	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Range
2019	7	4.714	1.799	1	6	5
2020	7	4.57	2.7	0	7	7
2021	7	5.286	1.604	3	7	4
2022	7	5.429	2.573	0	8	8

Source: Compilations from Minitab Statistical Software (21.2.0.0)

The descriptive statistics in Table 3 show that the mean environmental disclosure score increased from 4.714 in 2019 to 5.429 in 2022. This suggests that, on average, the level of environmental reporting by these companies has improved over this period. However, the minimum scores revealed some inconsistencies, with scores of 0.00 recorded in 2020 and 2022. This indicates that some companies still have very low levels of environmental disclosure, despite the overall improving trend. The maximum scores also increased to 8.00 by 2022, showcasing that some companies have substantially improved their environmental reporting. This suggests that while the industry is making progress, there is still significant variation in the level of environmental disclosures across different oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

In summary, environmental disclosures in the selected Nigerian oil and gas company have been improving on average, but some companies are still lagging in their environmental reporting practices. This portrayed the study by Wilson et al. (2020), which found inadequate reporting of sustainable economic performance, especially the financial implications and risks due to climate change, and the firm's less concern for environmental conservation due to weak law enforcement has now improved.

Table 4: Statistics of Social Disclosure Indicators Scores from the Annual Report Across Sample Companies (2019-2022)

Variable: Social Disclosure						
Year	Observations	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Range
2019	7	4.286	0.756	3	5	2
2020	7	4.143	0.9	3	5	2
2021	7	4.143	0.9	3	5	2
2022	7	4.143	1.864	0	5	5

Source: Compilations from Minitab Statistical Software (21.2.0.0)

The descriptive statistics presented in Table 4 show that the mean scores for social disclosures have remained relatively stable over the years, ranging from 4.143 to 4.286. This suggests that, on average, the level of social reporting by these companies did not change significantly during the period examined. The standard deviation values, which ranged from 0.756 to 1.864, indicate a moderate degree of variability in the social disclosure practices among the companies. This implies that while the average level of social reporting was relatively consistent, there were still differences in the extent of disclosure across the individual companies. The most concerning finding is the drop in the minimum scores to 0.00 in 2022, and this was because of the process of the voluntary winding up of the company among the observers. In contrast, the maximum scores remained consistently at 5.00 throughout the period. This suggests that the best-performing companies in terms of social reporting had reached the upper limit of the disclosure scale used in the analysis.

Only a small percentage, specifically 1.2%, of the corporations provided information regarding their political and financial donations. Most of the companies reported benefits to full-time employees, injury rates, representation of men and women in governance bodies, local community development programs, anti-corruption policies, and procedures. **Overall, 70% of the companies report on social disclosure more than the two other dimensions (economic and environmental). This answer the research question: ‘What dimension among the three—environment, economics, and social indicators of reporting—received more emphasis, and which ones were neglected?’**

5.3. One-way Repeated Measures Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Results.

One-way, repeated measurements ANOVA is also called within-subject ANOVA. It was used to see if the average of the sustainability disclosures was consistent across the seven groups of oil and gas firms. As a result, it was required to assess if there had been any changes in sustainability disclosures during the four years under study. A general linear model ANOVA: sustainability disclosure versus Year, Companies; was employed to assess variations in average sustainability disclosures across the seven groups of oil and gas companies. The dependent variable, sustainability disclosures, was measured on a continuous scale ranging from 0 to 22, while the independent variable comprised seven distinct categories corresponding to the observed years (2019 to 2022). The one-way repeated measures ANOVA is an appropriate statistical test to use to answer the research question about changes in sustainability disclosures across the oil and gas company groups over time.

As observed in Table 5, As observed in Table 5, The Ryan-Joiner test was employed to assess the normality of sustainability disclosures within the seven groups. It is important for properly analysing the sustainability disclosures of these oil and gas companies, as it helps identify deviations from the normal distribution that may have important implications for the statistical methods used and the interpretation of the results. The results indicated a departure from normal distribution, as evidenced by a significant p-value of less than 0.05 requiring further investigation in the future.

Table 5: Ryan-Joiner RJ test for normal data

Variable	Observations	RJ	P-Value
Total	28	0.925	<0.010
Sustainability Disclosure			

Source: Compilations from Minitab Statistical Software (21.2.0.0)

Table 6 below shows one-way repeated measures ANOVA was conducted on a sample of seven companies to determine whether there were disparities in sustainability disclosures over a four-year period, the analysis indicated non-significant differences in the average sustainability disclosures over the four-year period, with $F(6, 18) = 9.06$, $p < 0.01$, suggesting a consistent

trend in sustainability reporting practices among oil and gas companies from 2019 to 2022. This sheds light on the question ‘How do oil and gas companies in Nigeria report their sustainability engagement and involvement?’

Table 6: One-way repeated measure analysis of variance.

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Year	3	5.714	1.905	0.32	0.809
Companies	6	320.857	53.476	9.06	0.000
Error	18	106.286	5.905		
Total	27	432.857			
Number of Observations			28		
R-Squared			0.7545		
Adjusted R-Squared			0.6317		

Source: Compilations from Minitab Statistical Software (21.2.0.0)

5.4 Discussion of Findings

Companies are already used to financial reporting and incorporating economic indicators into sustainability reports. For example, community investments are frequently reported in financial statements. However, in this research effort, it was discovered that significant issues, including the risks and possibilities provided by climate change, its financial implications, and the cost of action taken on climate change, were not given sufficient attention by the firms. Similarly, this project's findings are related to the findings by Nwobu et al. (2021) that all companies reported their community investments, which the authors suggest may be a "legitimizing smokescreen" for ecological pollution.

The companies in 2022 have stepped up their reporting on environmental-sensitive indicators such as the number and volume of spills, gross direct greenhouse gas emissions, and water withdrawn for operations. These companies may see that reporting on the environment to be a key driver of improved financial performance, as Kabir Ibrahim et al.'s (2021) findings suggest that sustainability reporting, particularly in the environmental domain, plays a crucial role in

influencing the financial performance of listed Nigerian oil and gas companies. In summary, the companies have substantially improved their environmental reporting on all the indicators throughout the study period. This suggests that the industry is making progress as environmental disclosures in the sampled Nigerian oil and gas company have been improving on average. This sheds light on the question **‘How do oil and gas companies in Nigeria report their sustainability engagement and involvement?’**

Findings: Giving an answer to the research question ‘What dimension among the three—environment, economics, and social indicators of reporting—received more emphasis, and which ones were neglected?’

The essential indicators of sustainability reporting have been classified into economic, environmental, and social dimensions. This study discovered that these companies **report more on social indicators than any other dimension**, with a steady report on injury/injury rate/occupational disease rate, health and safety employee training, and local community development programs. This may serve as a social license to operate and showcase their commitment to sustainable development through the disclosure of their engagements with local communities and their support for community development initiatives (Oncioiu et al., 2020). This project's findings contradict a previous analysis (Raucci and Tarquinio, 2015), which found that labour disclosures dominated the social components of sustainability reporting. This research found that disclosures on injury/injury rate/occupational illness rates, health and safety staff training, and local community development activities were the most important social performance measures. Similarly, this study's findings do not agree with previous research (Raucci and Tarquinio, 2015; Ong et al., 2016), which revealed that corporations reported relatively low environmental indicators.

In the same vein, the empirical evidence presented by Iredele, O.O. (2020) confirms that the level of environmental reporting was very low. However, the findings of this research project reveal a notable increase in environmental reporting practices over the studied period. This observation suggests a positive trend towards enhanced transparency and disclosure of environmental information within the scope of the study. The longitudinal analysis conducted in this research highlights a considerable improvement in the quantity and quality of environmental reporting by the entities under examination, potentially indicating a growing recognition of the importance of such disclosures and a commitment to addressing stakeholder concerns regarding environmental impact and sustainability.

Findings: Giving an answer to the research question ‘What sustainability indicators do Nigerian oil and gas companies include and track in their public reporting? Do they align with global industry best practices?’

Overall, this study’s results agree with those of Ogiri et al. (2012) and Nwobu, O. et al. (2021), where the oil and gas companies in Nigeria tend to focus more on disclosing information about their social and community engagement activities than their environmental performance. This may suggest that these companies are primarily using sustainability reporting as a tool to manage their legitimacy and social acceptance rather than to comprehensively address their environmental impacts. This study’s findings also concur with the findings of Tijjani et al. (2020), where the quantity of information reported was discovered to be poor in comparison to reporting standards such as the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) framework, which is considered the global industry best practice.

The findings of this research, which also revealed increased sustainability reporting by the sampled company, align with the conclusions drawn by Ikpor, I. et al. (2022). Their study indicated that the oil and gas sector disclose a higher volume of sustainability information compared to the banking and industrial sectors investigated. This present study's findings corroborate the notion that industries with a more substantial environmental footprint exhibit a greater propensity to communicate their actions, potentially as a means of legitimizing their operations. This tendency can be interpreted as an attempt to mitigate potential reputational risks and foster a positive public perception regarding their environmental stewardship efforts.

5.5 Using legitimacy and reputation theory to explain the findings of the research.

Legitimacy theory and reputation theory provide valuable frameworks for understanding the findings of this research on sustainability reporting within Nigerian oil and gas companies.

Legitimacy Theory: Legitimacy theory posits that organizations engage in activities, such as sustainability reporting, to maintain their legitimacy in the eyes of society, stakeholders, and regulatory bodies. The findings of the research align with this theory in several ways:

Social Reporting Emphasis: Companies utilize social indicators in sustainability reporting, such as community development programs and health and safety efforts, to showcase their dedication to social responsibility and uphold their social license to operate. This aligns with the idea that companies use sustainability reporting to legitimize their operations by showcasing their positive societal impacts.

Environmental Reporting Improvement: The rise in environmental reporting throughout time is a direct response to the concerns and expectations of stakeholders and society around the influence on the environment and the need for sustainability. By enhancing transparency and disclosure of environmental information, companies aim to address stakeholders' demands for accountability and demonstrate their responsiveness to environmental issues, thus bolstering their legitimacy.

Comparison with Global Standards: The research findings suggest that Nigerian oil and gas corporations do not meet global reporting standards, such as the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) framework. This discrepancy implies that companies may engage in sustainability reporting not only to meet regulatory requirements but also to align themselves with global norms and expectations, thereby enhancing their legitimacy on an international scale.

Reputation Theory: Reputation theory suggests that organizations engage in actions, including sustainability reporting, to build and protect their reputation. The findings of the research resonate with this theory in the following ways:

Focus on Social and Community Engagement: The inclination of companies to emphasize disclosures concerning social and community involvement initiatives suggests a deliberate endeavour to effectively manage their reputation in a good manner. By highlighting their contributions to society and local communities, companies seek to enhance their reputations as socially responsible entities, thereby fostering goodwill and trust among stakeholders.

Increased Sustainability Reporting: The observed increase in sustainability reporting by oil and gas companies, particularly in response to growing environmental concerns, reflects a strategic attempt to safeguard and enhance their reputations. By proactively communicating their environmental stewardship efforts, companies aim to mitigate reputational risks associated with their environmental impact and demonstrate their commitment to sustainable practices.

Sectoral Comparison: The observation that the oil and gas industry provide a greater amount of sustainability information in comparison to other industries implies a deliberate and calculated reaction to reputation concerns that are peculiar to the sector. Given the sector's significant environmental footprint, companies may prioritize sustainability reporting as a means of mitigating reputational risks and projecting a positive image of their environmental performance.

In summary, the findings of the research underscore the interplay between legitimacy theory and reputation theory in shaping companies' sustainability reporting practices within the Nigerian oil and gas sector. By leveraging sustainability reporting as a tool to maintain legitimacy, manage reputation, and respond to stakeholder expectations, companies seek to navigate complex social, environmental, and economic dynamics while striving for long-term viability and success.

Chapter Six.

Conclusions

6.1 Conclusions

The assessment of sustainability reporting practices among selected Nigerian oil and gas companies reveals a gradual improvement in disclosure levels, albeit with significant variations across companies. While the reporting of economic and social sustainability indicators has been relatively consistent, environmental disclosures have witnessed notable progress over the years. However, the study findings reveal that these companies prioritize social responsibility and community engagement disclosures, potentially utilizing them as "Authorizing veneers" to manage their social license to operate amidst environmental impacts. Despite some improvement, the overall quality and comprehensiveness of sustainability reporting still lag global best practices, such as the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) framework.

6.2 Limitations of the Study

The sample may contain missing or inconsistent information because gaining direct access to sustainability managers for interviews and insights for more details that were not published may also be difficult due to availability and unresponsiveness, limiting data gathering to secondary sources. The study focuses primarily on publicly traded Nigerian oil and gas companies; the findings may only explain reporting methods in these companies and cannot be generalized to the larger industry, as there are some oil and gas companies that do not operate on the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE). The short 4-year span covered, along with reliance on self-reported firm disclosures, limits the capacity to objectively evaluate the accuracy and maturity of reported sustainability measures. While still providing value, these limitations highlight the need for more extensive research to expand understanding of oil and gas sustainability reporting in Nigeria in the long term.

6.3 Recommendations

For the government:

The government should implement more stringent sustainability disclosure policies and enforcement mechanisms to promote genuine environmental accountability and sustainable practices in the Nigerian oil and gas sector. This should be accompanied by capacity-building initiatives and stakeholder engagement to ensure effective adoption and compliance.

For oil and gas companies:

Oil and gas companies in Nigeria should strive to provide more comprehensive, transparent, and credible sustainability reporting that addresses environmental, social, and governance (ESG) impacts in a balanced manner by actively engaging with local communities and environmental groups to address concerns. This will help them manage legitimacy, reputation, and stakeholder expectations more effectively.

For the academic community:

Academics should conduct further research to provide deeper insights into the drivers, barriers, and impacts of sustainability reporting in the Nigerian oil and gas industry and promote sustainability reporting education and awareness, which can in turn inform policy development and industry best practices to enhance corporate sustainability and transparency.

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APPENDIX 1: SUSTAINABILITY DISCLOSURES CHECKLIST

Economic Indicators

Community Investments.

Risks and opportunities posed by climate change.

Financial implications of the risk and opportunity posed by climate change.

Costs of actions taken to manage risks or opportunities posed by climate change.

Financial assistance received from the government.

Spending on local suppliers at significant locations of operations.

Environmental Indicators

Renewable and non-renewable materials are used.

Materials used are recycled materials used to manufacture the organization's products and services.

Fuel/electricity/heating/cooling/steam consumption.

Reduction in energy consumption due to conservation.

Water was withdrawn for operations.

Gross direct greenhouse gas emissions.

Organic pollutants.

Waste and method of disposal.

Number and volume of spills.

Environmental protection expenditures.

Social Indicators

Benefits to full-time employees.

Injury/injury rate/occupational disease rate.

Health and safety employee training.

Representation of men and women in governance bodies.

Local community development programs.

Political, financial, and other kinds of contributions made directly and indirectly by the organization.

APPENDIX 2: The Study population

1	Mrs Oil Nigeria Plc
2	Capital Oil Plc
3	Eterna Plc
4	Japaul Gold & Ventures
5	Oando Plc
6	Rak Unity Pet. Comp
7	Total energies Marketing Nigeria Plc
8	Arдова Plc
9	Seplat Energy Plc
10	Conoil Plc

Source: Nigerian Exchange Group

APPENDIX 3: Sample size of the study

1	Mrs Oil Nigeria Plc
2	Total energies Marketing Nigeria Plc
3	Oando Plc
4	Conoil Plc
5	Eterna Plc
6	Seplat Energy Plc
7	Rak Unity Pet. Comp

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2024)

APPENDIX 4: Data retrieved from the annual report and stand-alone sustainability report across the sample companies (2019–2022) using content analysis.

INDICATOR	YEAR	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY
Economic Indicators	2019	Oando Plc	Total Energy	Conoil Plc	MRS	Eternal Plc	Seplat Energy	Rak Unity Pet.
Community Investments.		1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Risks and opportunities posed by climate change.		1	1	0	0	0	1	1
Financial implications of the risk and opportunity posed by climate change.		0	1	1	1	1	1	0
Costs of actions taken to manage risks or opportunities posed by climate change.		1	0	0	1	1	0	0
Financial assistance received from the government.		0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Spending on local suppliers at significant locations of operations.		0	0	1	1	0	1	0
Environmental Indicators								
Renewable and non-renewable materials are used.		1	1	0	1	0	0	1
Materials used are recycled materials used to manufacture the organization's products and services.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fuel/electricity/heating/cooling/steam consumption.		1	1	1	0	1	1	0
Reduction in energy consumption due to conservation.		1	1	1	0	1	1	0
Water was withdrawn for operations.		1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Gross direct greenhouse gas emissions.		0	1	1	0	0	1	0
Organic pollutants.		0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Waste and method of disposal.		1	1	0	1	1	1	0
Number and volume of spills.		1	1	0	1	0	1	0
Environmental protection expenditures.		0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Social Indicators								
Benefits to full-time employees.		1	0	1	1	1	1	0
Injury/injury rate/occupational disease rate.		1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Health and safety employee training.		1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Representation of men and women in governance bodies.		1	1	0	1	0	0	1
Local community development programs.		1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Political, financial, and other kinds of contributions made directly and indirectly by the organization.		0	0	1	0	0	0	0

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2024)

INDICATOR	YEAR	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY
	2020	Oando Plc	Total Energy	Conoil Plc	MRS	Eternal Plc	Seplat Energy	Rak Unity Pet
Economic Indicators								
Community Investments.		1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Risks and opportunities posed by climate change.		1	1	1	1	0	1	1
Financial implications of the risk and opportunity posed by climate change.		1	0	0	0	1	1	0
Costs of actions taken to manage risks or opportunities posed by climate change.		0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Financial assistance received from the government.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Spending on local suppliers at significant locations of operations.		1	1	1	1	0	1	0
Environmental Indicators								
Renewable and non-renewable materials are used.		1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Materials used are recycled materials used to manufacture the organization's products and services.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fuel/electricity/heating/cooling/steam consumption.		1	1	1	0	1	0	0
Reduction in energy consumption due to conservation.		1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Water was withdrawn for operations.		1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Gross direct greenhouse gas emissions.		1	1	1	1	0	1	0
Organic pollutants.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Waste and method of disposal.		1	1	1	0	1	1	0
Number and volume of spills.		1	1	1	0	0	1	0
Environmental protection expenditures.		0	0	0	0	1	1	0
Social Indicators								
Benefits to full-time employees.		1	0	1	1	1	0	1
Injury/injury rate/occupational disease rate.		1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Health and safety employee training.		1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Representation of men and women in governance bodies.		1	1	1	1	0	0	1
Local community development programs.		1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Political, financial, and other kinds of contributions made directly and indirectly by the organization.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2024)

INDICATOR	YEAR	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY
	2021	Oando Plc	Total Energy	Conoil Plc	MRS	Eternal Plc	Seplat Energy	Rak Unity Pet
Economic Indicators								
Community Investments.		1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Risks and opportunities posed by climate change.		1	1	0	1	1	1	0
Financial implications of the risk and opportunity posed by climate change.		1	1	0	1	0	1	1
Costs of actions taken to manage risks or opportunities posed by climate change.		0	1	0	0	1	1	1
Financial assistance received from the government.		0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Spending on local suppliers at significant locations of operations.		1	1	1	0	0	1	0
Environmental Indicators								
Renewable and non-renewable materials are used.		1	1	1	0	1	0	0
Materials used are recycled materials used to manufacture the organization's products and services.		0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Fuel/electricity/heating/cooling/steam consumption.		1	1	1	0	1	1	1
Reduction in energy consumption due to conservation.		1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Water was withdrawn for operations.		0	0	0	0	1	1	0
Gross direct greenhouse gas emissions.		1	1	0	1	0	1	1
Organic pollutants.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Waste and method of disposal.		1	1	1	0	1	1	0
Number and volume of spills.		1	1	0	1	1	1	0
Environmental protection expenditures.		0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Social Indicators								
Benefits to full-time employees.		1	1	1	0	1	0	1
Injury/injury rate/occupational disease rate.		1	1	1	0	1	1	1
Health and safety employee training.		1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Representation of men and women in governance bodies.		1	1	0	1	1	0	0
Local community development programs.		1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Political, financial, and other kinds of contributions made directly and indirectly by the organization.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2024)

INDICATOR	YEAR	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY	OIL & GAS COMPANY
		Oando Plc	Total Energy	Conoil Plc	MRS	Eternal Plc	Seplat Energy	Rak Unity Pet
Economic Indicators								
Community Investments.	2022	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
Risks and opportunities posed by climate change.		1	1	0	1	1	1	0
Financial implications of the risk and opportunity posed by climate change.		0	1	1	1	1	1	0
Costs of actions taken to manage risks or opportunities posed by climate change.		1	0	1	1	1	0	0
Financial assistance received from the government.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Spending on local suppliers at significant locations of operations.		1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Environmental Indicators								
Renewable and non-renewable materials are used.		1	1	0	0	1	0	0
Materials used are recycled materials used to manufacture the organization's products and services.		1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fuel/electricity/heating/cooling/steam consumption.		1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Reduction in energy consumption due to conservation.		1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Water was withdrawn for operations.		1	1	1	0	1	1	0
Gross direct greenhouse gas emissions.		1	1	1	1	0	1	0
Organic pollutants.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Waste and method of disposal.		1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Number and volume of spills.		1	1	0	0	1	0	0
Environmental protection expenditures.		0	0	1	1	0	1	0
Social Indicators								
Benefits to full-time employees.		1	1	1	0	1	1	0
Injury/injury rate/occupational disease rate.		1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Health and safety employee training.		1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Representation of men and women in governance bodies.		1	1	0	1	1	1	0
Local community development programs.		1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Political, financial, and other kinds of contributions made directly and indirectly by the organization.		0	0	1	0	0	0	0

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2024)

APPENDIX 5: Total Sustainability Disclosure scores derived from reports of the sample companies between 2019 and 2022 using content analysis.

Year	Companies	Sustainability Disclosure
2019	Oando Plc	14
2019	Total Energy	13
2019	Conoil Plc	14
2019	MRS	14
2019	Eternal Plc	11
2019	Seplat Energy	14
2019	Rak Unity Petroleum	5
2020	Oando Plc	16
2020	Total Energy	13
2020	Conoil Plc	16
2020	MRS	10
2020	Eternal Plc	11
2020	Seplat Energy	13
2020	Rak Unity Petroleum	4
2021	Oando Plc	15
2021	Total Energy	17
2021	Conoil Plc	11
2021	MRS	9
2021	Eternal Plc	14
2021	Seplat Energy	15
2021	Rak Unity Petroleum	10
2022	Oando Plc	17
2022	Total Energy	16
2022	Conoil Plc	15
2022	MRS	12
2022	Eternal Plc	15
2022	Seplat Energy	14
2022	Rak Unity Petroleum	0

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2024)

Appendix 6: Total Economic, Environmental, and Social Dimensions of Sustainability Disclosure Scores retrieved from the reports of the sample companies between 2019 and 2022 using content analysis.

Year	Companies	Economic Disclosure	Environmental Disclosure	Social Disclosure
2019	Oando Plc	3	6	5
2019	Total Energy	3	6	4
2019	Conoil Plc	4	5	5
2019	MRS	4	5	5
2019	Eternal Plc	3	4	4
2019	Seplat Energy	4	6	4
2019	Rak Unity Petroleum	1	1	3
2020	Oando Plc	4	7	5
2020	Total Energy	3	6	4
2020	Conoil Plc	4	7	5
2020	MRS	3	2	5
2020	Eternal Plc	3	4	4
2020	Seplat Energy	4	6	3
2020	Rak Unity Petroleum	1	0	3
2021	Oando Plc	4	6	5
2021	Total Energy	5	7	5
2021	Conoil Plc	3	4	4
2021	MRS	3	3	3
2021	Eternal Plc	3	6	5
2021	Seplat Energy	5	7	3
2021	Rak Unity Petroleum	2	4	4
2022	Oando Plc	4	8	5
2022	Total Energy	4	7	5
2022	Conoil Plc	4	6	5
2022	MRS	3	5	4
2022	Eternal Plc	4	6	5
2022	Seplat Energy	3	6	5
2022	Rak Unity Petroleum	0	0	0

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2024)

APPENDIX 7: Outliers

Source: Compilations from Minitab Statistical Software (21.2.0.0)

APPENDIX 8: Normal Plot of Sustainability Disclosure

Source: Compilations from Minitab Statistical Software (21.2.0.0)

APPENDIX 9: ETHICS APPROVAL

Cardiff
Metropolitan
University

Prifysgol
Metropolitan
Caerdydd

APPLICATION FOR ETHICS APPROVAL

When undertaking a research or innovation project, Cardiff Met staff and students are obliged to complete this form in order that the ethics implications of that project may be considered.

The document *Ethics application guidance notes* will help you complete this form and is available from the Ethics Governance Section of the Cardiff Met website. The School or Unit in which you are based may also have produced some guidance documents which you can access via your supervisor or School Ethics Coordinator.

PLEASE

NOTE:

Participant recruitment or data collection MUST NOT commence until ethics approval has been obtained.

PART ONE

1A: GENERAL INFORMATION	
Name of applicant:	Kilani Ibrahim
Supervisor (if student project):	Dr Zhang Jun
School / Unit:	School of Management
Student number (if applicable):	St20253822
Programme enrolled on (if applicable):	International Business Management
Project Title: If using a working title, it should convey what	An Assessment of Sustainability Reporting in some Selected Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria
Expected start date of data collection:	1 st April, 2024
Approximate duration of data collection:	2 Weeks
Funding Body (if applicable):	-
Other researcher(s) working on the project: If your collaborators are external to Cardiff Met, include details of the organisation they	-
Will the study involve NHS patients or staff? If yes, attach a copy of your NHS application	No

Will the study involve human samples and/or human cell lines?	No
---	----

1B: Does your project fall entirely within one of the following categories:	
Desk based, involving only documents and not involving the collection of data from participants	Yes
Laboratory based, not involving human participants, human samples, animals or animal derived material	No
Practice based not involving human participants (eg curatorial, practice audit)	No
<p>Answering YES to any of these questions indicates that the project does not include any participants and you will not therefore be collecting participant data. If this is the case, please provide a short (150 words) non-technical summary of the project, complete the Declaration at the bottom of the form and forward this form to your School Ethics Committee (or equivalent).</p> <p>No further information regarding your project is required and you do not need to complete any more sections of this form. The only exception to this is in relation to projects which include security sensitive research – see below for further details.</p> <p>If you have answered NO to all of these questions, please proceed to 1C.</p>	
<p>Provide a non-technical summary of the project below.</p> <p>NB: Any project which includes security sensitive research will be referred to the Prevent Co-ordinator so it can be risk assessed in line with the Prevent Policy. Ethics approval will only be granted once the Prevent Co-ordinator is content with the outcomes of that risk assessment.</p>	
<p>My research project will assess the status of sustainability reporting among selected major Nigerian oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange, to what extent the sustainability reports of these oil and gas companies cover key issues like health and safety, environment, community relations, and governance, and which dimensions receive more emphasis and which ones are neglected. To identify gaps and areas of weakness, if any, in their current reporting system. My research will be based on secondary data. Data will be analysed using a content analysis of sustainability disclosures in the annual reports of the seven (7) oil and gas companies in Nigeria, utilizing the Global Reporting Initiative’s scoring index, and drawing conclusions from this analysis as to whether these companies are complying with the global best practice of sustainability reporting.</p>	

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1C: Does your project fall entirely within one of the following categories:	
Compulsory projects in professional practice (eg Initial Teacher Education)	Yes / No
<p>A project for which NHS approval has been obtained</p> <p>NB If this is the case, please ensure that you submit copies of the following with this form:</p> <p>any questionnaires to be used</p> <p>participant consent / asset form and withdrawal form</p> <p>participant information sheets</p>	Yes / No
<p>A project which is not compulsory in professional practice and has gained external ethics approval from a body other than the NHS.</p> <p>NB If this is the case, please ensure that you submit a copy of the approved ethics application with this form.</p>	Yes/ No
<p>If you have answered YES to any of these questions, please provide a short (150 words) non-technical summary of the project and complete the rest of Part One of this form. You do not need to complete Part Two.</p> <p>Forward your completed form, along with any additional documents required (as indicated above) to your School Ethics Committee (or equivalent).</p> <p>If you have answered NO to all of these questions, please complete the rest of this form including Part Two.</p>	
Provide a non-technical summary of the project below:	

1D: DATA COLLECTION AND STORAGE
What types of data will you collect or create?
Secondary data
How will you manage access to and security of the data?
Data stored in CMet OneDrive

<p>Will the data collected be subject to the data retention protocols of any of the following bodies? Human Tissue Authority (HTA) Health and Care Research Wales (HCRW) Applications involving the NHS which will be submitted via IRAS</p>	
<p>Yes ☐</p> <p>For any project which is subject to the data retention protocols of an external body listed, you must develop a data storage plan to be submitted alongside this document for consideration by your School or Unit Ethics Panel.</p>	
<p>No ☐</p> <p>Please confirm that the data collected will be stored in a manner which complies with Cardiff Met requirements via one of the following statements.</p>	
<p>STATEMENT 1: FOR STUDENTS ON TAUGHT COURSES</p> <p>I confirm that any non-anonymised data related to research participants will only be stored on OneDrive, or by agreement with supervising staff, on Figshare, and that all data held elsewhere will be deleted, unless it is anonymised.</p>	☒
<p>STATEMENT 2: FOR STAFF APPLYING ON BEHALF OF STUDENTS ON TAUGHT COURSES</p> <p>I confirm that all students covered by this application are aware of their obligation to ensure that non-anonymised data related to research participants must only be stored on their Cardiff Met student OneDrive account and that all data held elsewhere must be deleted, unless it is anonymised.</p>	☐
<p>STATEMENT 3: FOR RESEARCH STUDENTS AND STAFF</p> <p>I confirm that any non-anonymised data related to research participants will be stored in a secure manner (using a platform such as OneDrive or FigShare) and that all data held elsewhere will be deleted unless it is anonymised.</p>	☐

DECLARATION:

I confirm that this project conforms with the [Cardiff Met Research Integrity & Governance Framework](#)

I confirm that I will abide by the Cardiff Met requirements regarding confidentiality and anonymity when conducting this project.

STUDENTS: I confirm that I will not disclose any information about this project without the prior approval of my supervisor.

Signature of the applicant:

Kilani Ibrahim

Date: 8th March, 2024

FOR STUDENT PROJECTS ONLY

Name of supervisor:

Jun Zhang

Date: 12th March 2024

Signature of supervisor:

张俊

Research Ethics Committee use only

Decision reached:

[Click here to enter text.](#)

Project reference number: [Click here to enter text.](#)

Name: [Click here to enter text.](#)

Date: [Click here to enter a date.](#)

Details of any conditions upon which approval is dependant:

[Click here to enter text.](#)

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Metropolitan
University

Prifysgol
Metropolitan
Caerdydd

APPLICATION FOR ETHICS APPROVAL

PART TWO

If you haven't already done so elsewhere on this form, in the box below, provide a short (150 words), non-technical summary of the project.

A RESEARCH DESIGN

A1 Will you be using an approved protocol in your project?

Yes / No

A2 If yes, please state the name and code of the approved protocol to be used¹

A3 Describe the research design to be used in your project

In this section, include details (as appropriate) of:

Research method(s);

Sample and sampling;

Participants including recruitment methods, activities to be undertaken, time commitment, details of any proposed payments;

Analytical techniques

If your project does involve the use of an approved protocol, much less details will be required but you should indicate which areas of the project are covered by the protocol.

A4 Will the project involve deceptive or covert research?

Yes / No

A5 If yes, give a rationale for the use of deceptive or covert research

¹ An Approved Protocol is one which has been approved by Cardiff Met to be used under supervision of designated members of staff. For details of protocols in use in your School or Unit, contact your Ethics Coordinator

<p>A6 Will the project have security sensitive implications?</p> <p>NB: Any project which falls under this definition will be referred to the Prevent Co-ordinator by the Committee which is considering the application so it can be risk assessed in line with the Prevent Policy. Ethics approval will only be granted once the Prevent Co-ordinator is content with the outcomes of that risk assessment.</p>	Yes / No
<p>A7 If yes, please explain what they are and the measures that are proposed to address them</p>	

B PREVIOUS EXPERIENCE

B1 What previous experience of research involving human participants relevant to this project do you have?

[Click here to enter text.](#)

2	<p>Student project only</p>
<p>What previous experience of research involving human participants relevant to this project does your supervisor have?</p>	
<p>Click here to enter text.</p>	

C POTENTIAL RISKS

C1 What potential risks do you foresee?

Include details of risks to the participants, the researcher and the project as a whole.

C2 How will you deal with the potential risks?

When submitting your application you **MUST** attach a copy of the following:

- All information sheets
- Consent/assent form(s)
- Withdrawal of consent form

An exemplar information sheet, exemplar participant consent form and exemplar participant withdrawal form are available via the research section of the Cardiff Met website (see section on Ethics Governance). These are based on good practice and will be useful in the majority of

cases. However, it is recognised that in some cases a project will be subject to requirements from an external body. Use of these exemplars is therefore not obligatory.

Devolved Ethical Approval Panel (DEAP): Application Summary

Student Name: Kilani Ibrahim Student Number: st20253822

Module Name: International Research Project Module Number: MSM7037

Programme Name: MSc International Business Management Supervisor Name: Dr Zhang Jun

To be completed by student <u>and</u> supervisor before submission to Ethics Approval Panel	Student Signature;		Supervisor Signature; Jun Zhang	
	Yes	N/A	Yes	N/A
Application for ethics approval	☐	-	☐	-
Participant information sheet	☐	☐	☐	☐
Participant consent form	☐	☐	☐	☐
Pilot interview/s	☐	☐	☐	☐
Pilot questionnaire/s	☐	☐	☐	☐
Letter/s to participating organisation/s	☐	☐	☐	☐
Confirmation of interviewee participation	☐	☐	☐	☐
Participant withdrawal form	☐	☐	☐	☐

First Submission [Yes] Resubmission []

Date: 8th March, 2024

For use by the devolved ethics approval panel:

<u>Panel Members</u>	<u>Name</u>	<u>Signature</u>
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Module leader, Chair:	<u>Francesca Mariotti</u>	<u>Francesca Mariotti</u>
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James Whitehead	<u>J. Whitehead.</u>	
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Supervisor:	<u>Jun Zhang</u>	<u>J. Zhang</u>
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CSM Ethics Committee Representative:

Date: 26/03/2024

Date of Reassessment:

Outcome:

Project Approved Reference number: 2023.24DE1313

Project Approved in Principle

Decision deferred (application not ready/incomplete)

Project Not Approved (major revisions)

Project Rejected

Comments for projects not fully approved:

The original to be retained by the supervisor and a copy given to the student and module leader.

*In the case of a resubmission being required this **original form** should be submitted with the resubmission.*

APPENDIX 10: Meeting Record Form.

MSM7037 International Research Project

AGREED MEETING SCHEDULE

This form should be completed at the beginning of the supervisory process. Supervisor and the student should retain a copy. A copy must be included in the Appendices of your final dissertation submission.

*Students must meet with their supervisor face-to-face at least **THREE TIMES** to discuss their progress. This will be supplemented by an appropriate amount of e-mail support.*

Student's Name: 20253822 Ibrahim Kilani

Supervisor: Dr Jun Zhang

Proposed Dates of Meeting and Research Progress Monitoring:

1st Meeting Date: 12/03/24_____ Estimated Duration: 30 minutes

2nd Meeting Date: 20/03/24_____ Estimated Duration: 30 minutes

3rd Meeting Date: 28/03/24_____ Estimated Duration: 30 minutes

Student's signature: Kilani Ibrahim

Date: 30/04/24

Supervisor's signature:

Date:

MSM7037 International Research Project

SUPERVISION RECORD

*This form should be completed at **each** supervisory meeting. Supervisor and the student should retain a copy. A copy must be included in the Appendices of your final dissertation submission.*

Student's Name: 20253822 Ibrahim Kilani

Supervisor: Dr Jun Zhang

Date of Meeting: 12/03/24

Time: 10.30-11.00

Written work submitted or other purpose of meeting:

Meeting 1

Main topics/issues discussed and action points agreed:

Discussed the nature of the research. Focusing on sustainability reporting of the oil and gas sector of Nigeria. Discussed the rationale for choosing this topic and the reason for selecting oil and gas industry. You demonstrated the data base where you search for academic journals.

You need to read more of the academic research/journals that researched in this area. There were 7 identified that link to Nigeria and sustainability reporting. More research needs to be done on this. You need to find out more about the oil and gas sector of Nigeria. More reading is required on sustainability reporting overall, research on developed countries, research compare and contrast developed and developing countries. You need to think what kind of analysis can be conducted.

Time, date and location of next meeting:

20th March 10.30 Teams

Actions and agenda topics for next meeting:

See above

Student's signature: Kilani Ibrahim

Date: 12/03/24

Supervisor's signature: Jun Zhang

Date: 12/03/24

MSM7037 International Research Project

SUPERVISION RECORD

*This form should be completed at **each** supervisory meeting. Supervisor and the student should retain a copy. A copy must be included in the Appendices of your final dissertation submission.*

Student's Name: 20253822 Ibrahim Kilani

Supervisor: Dr Jun Zhang

Date of Meeting: 20/03/24

Time: 10.30-11.00

Written work submitted or other purpose of meeting:

Meeting 2

Main topics/issues discussed and action points agreed:

You addressed the items in the previous meeting notes. Discussed the research in this area and research questions.

Time, date and location of next meeting:

28th March 10.00 Teams

Actions and agenda topics for next meeting:

You need to further your research and reading. You need to know which companies in Oil and Gas that operate in Nigeria. You need to consider what kind of analysis should be considered so you have the answers for your research questions.

Student's signature: Kilani Ibrahim

Date: 20/03/24

Supervisor's signature: Jun Zhang

Date: 20/03/24

MSM7037 International Research Project

SUPERVISION RECORD

*This form should be completed at **each** supervisory meeting. Supervisor and the student should retain a copy. A copy must be included in the Appendices of your final dissertation submission.*

Student's Name: 20253822 Ibrahim Kilani

Supervisor: Dr Jun Zhang

Date of Meeting: 28/03/24

Time: 10.00-10.30

Written work submitted or other purpose of meeting:

Meeting 3

Main topics/issues discussed and action points agreed:

You addressed the items in the previous meeting notes.

Time, date and location of next meeting:

TBC

Actions and agenda topics for next meeting:

You need to start drafting the chapters.

Student's signature: Kilani Ibrahim

Date: 28/03/24

Supervisor's signature: Jun Zhang

Date: 28/03/24

MSM7037 International Research Project

SUPERVISION RECORD

*This form should be completed at **each** supervisory meeting. Supervisor and the student should retain a copy. A copy must be included in the Appendices of your final dissertation submission.*

Student's Name: 20253822 Ibrahim Kilani

Supervisor: Dr Jun Zhang

Date of Meeting: 03/05/24

Time: 9.30-10.00

Written work submitted or other purpose of meeting:

Meeting 4

Main topics/issues discussed and action points agreed:

To explain how data is gathered and analysed.

Time, date and location of next meeting:

Actions and agenda topics for next meeting:

Student's signature: Kilani Ibrahim

Date: 03/05/24

Supervisor's signature: Jun Zhang

Date: 03/05/24

